

Pre-Stroke Antiplatelet use and Clinical Outcome in Patients with Ischemic Stroke in a Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Stroke remains a significant cause of death and disability globally. The use of pre-stroke antiplatelet (PAP) therapy has been shown to influence stroke severity and outcomes, though findings from various studies have been mixed. This study aims to investigate the effect of pre-stroke antiplatelet use on stroke severity, early neurological deterioration (END), and long-term functional outcomes in acute ischemic stroke (IS) patients, focusing on differences across stroke subtypes.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted from September 2022 to August 2024, involving 600 patients with their first-ever ischemic stroke admitted within 24 hours of symptom onset. Patients were classified based on prior use of antiplatelet agents, and stroke subtypes were identified using the TOAST classification (large artery atherosclerosis [AT], small artery disease [SAD], and cardio-embolic [CE] stroke). Stroke severity was measured using the NIH Stroke Scale (NIHSS) at admission, and functional recovery was evaluated using the modified Rankin Scale (mRS) at three months. Clinical outcomes including END, recurrent ischemic stroke (RIS), hemorrhagic transformation (HT), and mortality were also assessed.

Results: Out of the 600 participants, 137 (22.83%) had taken antiplatelet agents prior to their stroke. PAP users had significantly lower NIHSS scores upon admission, particularly in patients with AT stroke ($P < 0.001$). Antiplatelet use was linked to a reduced risk of END (HR: 0.78; 95% CI: 0.56–0.91; $P = 0.03$) and better functional outcomes at three months (mRS ≤ 2 ; 48.9% vs. 21.6%, $P < 0.001$), despite an elevated risk of asymptomatic HT (HR: 1.35; 95% CI: 1.08–3.07; $P = 0.001$). The positive impact of PAP use on functional outcomes was observed across all stroke subtypes.

Conclusion: Pre-stroke antiplatelet therapy is associated with reduced stroke severity, particularly in large artery atherosclerosis, and leads to better functional outcomes at three months, irrespective of stroke subtype. Despite an increased risk of asymptomatic hemorrhagic transformation, the overall clinical benefit of antiplatelet use in acute ischemic stroke is evident.

Keywords: Prestroke anti-platelet use, Ischemic stroke, early neurological deterioration, Hemorrhagic transformation, Outcome.

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Introduction

Stroke ranks as the second most prevalent cause of death globally and is a leading contributor to long-term disability worldwide [1]. In recent years, the use of antiplatelet medications has risen among individuals with diabetes and cardiovascular diseases [2-4]. A study from the UK reported a more than tenfold increase in pre-stroke antiplatelet use, from 2.9% in 1984 to 33.6% in 2004 [4].

Antiplatelet agents play a crucial role in preventing strokes following a transient ischemic attack (TIA) or an ischemic stroke, with potential additional benefits in reducing stroke severity [5]. Pre-stroke antiplatelet therapy can influence both the severity and outcomes of a stroke. Several studies have

explored the impact of aspirin, a common antiplatelet agent, on reducing stroke severity [6-9]. These studies have produced mixed results, with some indicating decreased odds of severe stroke and disability at discharge with pre-stroke antiplatelet therapy [10-15].

Clinical outcomes and stroke severity may vary across different stroke subtypes. Kim et al. [16] found that the reduction in baseline NIHSS scores between antiplatelet users and non-users was significant only in patients with large artery atherosclerosis, not in those with cardio-embolic stroke or small vessel occlusion. This study aims to evaluate whether pre-stroke use of antiplatelet

agents affects stroke severity, clinical outcomes including early neurological deterioration (END), recurrent ischemic stroke (RIS), and death during the three months following admission, and functional outcomes (measured by the modified Rankin Scale [mRS]) at three months, according to stroke subtypes, compared to patients not taking antiplatelet agents.

Materials and Methods

This prospective observational study was conducted at Tirunelveli Medical College Hospital from September 2022 to August 2024. The study protocol received approval from the Ethics Committee of the participating hospital, and informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study.

We consecutively enrolled patients with acute ischemic stroke (IS) who met the following criteria: experiencing their first-ever stroke, admitted within 24 hours of symptom onset, and exhibiting relevant cerebral lesions on diffusion-weighted magnetic resonance imaging (DWI) consistent with acute IS. All patients underwent baseline brain computed tomography (CT) scans and magnetic resonance imaging upon admission. Additional CT assessments were performed if neurological deterioration occurred. CT angiography (CTA) or magnetic resonance angiography of the brain, as well as color duplex ultrasound examinations of the carotid arteries, were conducted for all patients. Electrocardiograms (ECG) and echocardiograms were also performed to detect potential cardio-embolic (CE) sources of stroke.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age ≥ 40 years.
2. Stroke subtypes classified as large artery atherosclerosis (AT), small artery disease (SAD), or cardio-embolic (CE) stroke according to the Trial of ORG 10172 in Acute Stroke Treatment (TOAST) classification system¹⁷.
3. Patients were divided into two groups based on pre-admission antiplatelet use: those on any antiplatelet agent (including aspirin, clopidogrel, ticlopidine, or aspirin/extended-release dipyridamole) and those not on any antiplatelet agents (including those taking only anticoagulants or no antithrombotic therapy at all).

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Other determined or undetermined etiology of IS.
2. History of carotid stent therapy or carotid endarterectomy.
3. Presence of fever, hypoxia, or significant hemodynamic compromise at admission.

4. History of asthma, severe cardiovascular disease, liver or renal disease.
5. Individuals who declined to participate.
6. Lack of information on study variables necessary for analysis.

Baseline Data Collection:

At baseline, the following information was collected:

1. Demographic data: age, sex, systolic and diastolic blood pressures at presentation.
2. Medical history: hypertension, diabetes mellitus, hyperlipidemia, smoking status, and coronary artery disease (CAD).
3. Hyperlipidemia was defined as total cholesterol (TC) >200 mg/dL, triglycerides (TG) >180 mg/dL, or use of lipid-lowering medication.

Stroke Severity and Clinical Outcomes

Each patient's stroke severity was assessed using the National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) upon admission and daily during hospitalization. Initial stroke severity was determined by the NIHSS score at admission. Functional outcomes were evaluated using the modified Rankin Scale (mRS) at three months post-admission. Good functional outcomes were defined as an mRS score of ≤ 2 , while poor outcomes were defined as an mRS score > 2 .

Clinical Outcomes Included:

1. **Early Neurological Deterioration (END):** Defined as an increase of two or more points in the NIHSS score within 10 days after admission, excluding hemorrhagic transformation (HT) of the infarct or a new infarct in another vascular territory.
2. **Composite Ischemic Events:** Including recurrent ischemic stroke (RIS), myocardial infarction (MI), and death during the three months after admission. RIS was defined as a new focal neurological deficit of vascular origin lasting at least 24 hours, confirmed by a DWI-positive lesion corresponding to clinical symptoms and proven to be non-hemorrhagic. Death was defined as vascular mortality due to MI, IS, or other vascular causes.
3. **Hemorrhagic Episodes:** Including any degree of hyperdensity within the area of low attenuation (HT) during two weeks after admission, intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH), and extracranial bleeding events.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 25.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). All tests were two-sided, with a significance threshold set at $P < 0.05$. Baseline characteristics, initial stroke severity, clinical outcomes, and functional outcomes between pre-admission antiplatelet (PAP) users and non-users were compared using univariate methods.

Categorical variables are presented as percentages and were compared using the Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. Continuous variables are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and were compared using the Student's t-test for normally distributed data; otherwise, non-parametric tests were used.

Multivariable logistic regression with the proportional odds model was employed to evaluate the effects of antiplatelet use on good functional outcomes at three months, incorporating variables with $P < 0.1$ from univariate analysis²². Cox proportional hazards regression analysis was conducted to examine the effects of antiplatelet use on the occurrence of HT and END, reported as hazard ratios (HR) with 95% confidence intervals

(CI). Variables included in the Cox models to adjust for confounding effects were those with imbalances ($P < 0.1$) identified in univariate analysis.

Results

Baseline Characteristics

A total of 600 patients meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Among them, 137 patients (22.83%) reported antiplatelet use within seven days before stroke onset. Baseline characteristics are presented in Table 1. Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) were observed for age, hypertension, and history of CAD between PAP users and non-users. No significant differences were found for other risk factors.

Table 1: Characteristics of study patients

Variable	PA user(n= 137)	Non- PA user(n=463)	P - value
Age	61.96 \pm 6.74	57.45 \pm 9.91	0.001
Gender			
Male	100 (73.0)	337 (72.8)	0.962
Female	37 (27.0)	126 (27.2)	
Smoker			
Yes	61 (44.5)	241 (52.1)	0.144
No	76 (55.5)	222 (47.9)	
Alcoholic			
Yes	66 (48.2)	203 (43.8)	0.380
No	71 (51.8)	260 (56.2)	
Hypertension			
Yes	98 (71.53)	266 (57.5)	0.001
No	39 (28.46)	197 (42.5)	
Diabetes			
Yes	77 (56.2)	265 (57.2)	0.845
No	60 (43.8)	198 (42.8)	
CAD			
Yes	76 (55.47)	120 (25.9)	0.001
No	61 (44.52)	343 (74.1)	
Hyperlipidemia			
Yes	84 (61.3)	285 (61.6)	0.959
No	53 (38.7)	178 (38.4)	
Type of stroke subtype			
Large vessel disease	68 (49.6)	255 (55.1)	0.241
Small artery disease	54 (39.4)	147 (31.7)	
Cardio embolism	15 (10.9)	61 (13.2)	
m RS Score at admission			
<2	18 (13.1)	43 (9.3)	0.199
>2	119 (86.9)	420 (90.7)	

Initial Stroke Severity: PAP users had significantly lower initial NIHSS scores compared to non-users ($P < 0.001$). Specifically, among patients with the AT stroke subtype, PAP users had lower NIHSS scores

than non-users ($P < 0.001$). No significant differences in initial NIHSS scores were observed between PAP users and non-users with SAD or CE stroke subtypes ($P > 0.05$, Table 2).

Table: 2 Comparison of NIHSS scores on admission between the antiplatelet and non-antiplatelet users according to stroke subtype.

Variable	PA user (N = 137)	Non- PA user (N = 463)	P - value
Total	(14.87 ± 3.53)	(16.72 ± 3.87)	0.001
Large vessel disease	(17.8 ± 2.23)	(20.11 ± 2.17)	0.001
Small artery disease	(12.9 ± 1.80)	(13.10 ± 2.24)	0.254
Cardio embolism	(15.2 ± 1.53)	(16.9 ± 2.71)	0.158

Clinical Outcomes: All participants completed the three-month follow-up. A total of 167 patients (27.83%) experienced END within ten days after admission. Of these, 21 cases (15.32%) occurred among PAP users, and 146 cases (31.5%) occurred among non-users. PAP users had a lower incidence of END compared to non-users (P=0.003, Table 3).

Table 3: The association between antiplatelet use and outcomes.

Variable	PA user	Non- PA user	P - value
m RS Score at admission			
<2	18 (13.1)	43 (9.3)	0.199
>2	119 (86.9)	420 (90.7)	
END(Early neurological deterioration)			
Yes	21 (15.32)	146 (31.5)	0.003
No	116 (84.67)	317 (68.5)	
RIS (Recurrent ischemic stroke)			
Yes	12 (8.8)	88 (19.0)	0.456
No	125 (91.2)	375 (81.0)	
Death	5(3.64)	12(2.5)	0.859
Hemorrhagic transformation			
Total	17 (13.1)	33(7.1)	0.045
Asymptomatic HT	13 (10)	25 (5.3)	0.035
Symptomatic HT	4 (3)	8 (1.72)	0.418
ICH	2 (1.4)	7 (1.54)	0.935
m RS @ 3 months			
<2	67 (48.9)	100 (21.6)	0.001
>2	70 (51.1)	363 (78.4)	

Cox proportional hazards regression analysis indicated that antiplatelet use was independently associated with a decreased risk of END after adjusting for confounding variables, including age, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, smoking status, hyperlipidemia, and NIHSS scores at admission (HR: 0.78; 95% CI: 0.56–0.91; P=0.03, Table 4).

Table: 4 Cox regression analysis the effect of pre-stroke antiplatelet use on early neurological deterioration

Factor	HR	95% CI	P value
Age	1.03	1.01 – 1.05	0.001
Smoker	0.81	0.57 – 1.12	0.272
Alcoholic	0.67	0.60 – 1.25	0.598
Hypertension	0.69	0.48 – 0.99	0.046
Diabetes	0.87	0.59 – 1.59	0.592
CAD	0.38	0.89 – 2.15	0.152
Hyperlipidemia	0.88	0.88 – 0.62	0.492
NIHSS	0.59	0.42 – 0.77	0.234
Pre stroke antiplatelet	0.78	0.56-0.91	0.030

HT occurred in 50 patients (8.3%) within two weeks of admission, with 17 cases (12.40%) among PAP users and 33 cases (7.12%) among non-users. PAP users exhibited a higher incidence of HT compared to non-users (P=0.045, Table 3). However, antiplatelet use was associated only with an increased risk of asymptomatic HT; no significant differences were observed in the rates of

symptomatic HT, ICH, or extracranial bleeding between the two groups. The increased risk of HT among PAP users remained significant in the Cox proportional hazards regression after adjusting for covariates, including age, alcohol consumption, smoking status, hypertension, diabetes, CAD, and NIHSS at admission (HR: 1.35; 95% CI: 1.08–3.07; P=0.001, Table 5).

Table: 5 Cox regression analysis the effect of pre-stroke antiplatelet use on hemorrhagic transformation

Factor	HR	95% CI	P value
Age	0.98	0.97 – 0.99	0.034
Smoker	1.09	0.91 – 1.30	0.373
Alcoholic	0.96	0.80 – 1.15	0.655
Hypertension	1.08	0.87 – 1.30	0.424
Diabetes	1.05	0.87 – 1.26	0.586
CAD	1.07	0.87 – 1.32	0.524
Hyperlipidemia	0.84	0.70 – 1.02	0.275
NIHSS at admission	0.90	0.78 – 1.25	0.702
Pre stroke antiplatelet	1.35	1.08 – 3.07	0.001

Good functional outcomes (mRS ≤ 2) at three months were achieved by a significantly higher percentage of PAP users compared to non-users (48.9% vs. 21.6%, $P < 0.001$, Table 3).

Antiplatelet use improved functional outcomes at three months despite an increased risk of HT,

regardless of stroke subtype (Table 3). Multivariable logistic regression analysis confirmed that antiplatelet use was significantly associated with good functional outcomes after adjusting for covariates (odds ratio: 1.47; 95% CI: 1.23–2.56; $P = 0.001$, Table 6).

Table: 6 Logistic regression analysis the effect of Pre stroke antiplatelet use on good functional outcome at 3 months after admission

Factor	OR	95% CI	P value
Age	2.09	1.42 – 3.08	0.001
Smoker	1.07	0.75 – 1.53	0.723
Alcoholic	1.45	1.01 – 2.07	0.042
Hypertension	1.13	1.13 – 0.77	0.576
Diabetes	0.75	0.53 – 1.09	0.142
CAD	0.49	0.31 – 0.79	0.373
Hyperlipidemia	2.31	1.55 – 3.43	0.001
Type of stroke subtype	0.23	0.17 – 0.30	0.302
NIHSS	1.96	1.75 – 2.19	0.001
Pre stroke antiplatelet	1.47	1.23-2.56	0.001

Discussion

The primary findings of this study are:

1. Pre-stroke antiplatelet use is associated with reduced initial stroke severity, particularly in patients with AT stroke subtype, but not in those with SAD or CE stroke subtypes.
2. Antiplatelet use independently correlates with a decreased risk of END within ten days post-admission.
3. While antiplatelet use increases the risk of HT, this association is limited to asymptomatic HT, with no significant impact on symptomatic HT.
4. Antiplatelet use is linked to improved functional outcomes (mRS ≤ 2) at three months post-admission across all stroke subtypes, despite the increased risk of HT.

Potential mechanisms by which antiplatelet agents may reduce stroke severity include plaque stabilization and decreased platelet aggregation, leading to reduced size and frequency of thromboembolic events [18,19]. Additionally, antiplatelet agents like aspirin may offer neuroprotective and anti-inflammatory benefits beyond their primary antithrombotic effects [18,20-

23]. Aspirin's antipyretic properties may also mitigate the detrimental effects of hyperthermia in stroke patients [24]. Our results suggest that the beneficial effect of antiplatelet therapy on reducing stroke severity is more pronounced in AT stroke subtype. This may be due to the mechanism of artery-to-artery embolism prevalent in AT stroke [25]. Aspirin may reduce the likelihood of embolization from unstable plaques and decrease emboli size [26]. In contrast, antiplatelet therapy may be less effective in SAD and CE strokes. Intensive antiplatelet therapy may increase bleeding risk in SAD stroke [27], and aspirin has minimal effects in preventing CE stroke, particularly in atrial fibrillation patients [28,29]. END is a serious complication associated with poor prognosis after acute IS [30,31]. Preventing END is crucial in acute IS management. Some studies have indicated that dual antiplatelet therapy with aspirin and clopidogrel is more effective in reducing END risk [32,34].

Our findings demonstrate that pre-stroke antiplatelet use is associated with a decreased risk of END. Platelet activation, thrombus extension, and pro-inflammatory cytokines play significant roles in

END pathogenesis [35,36]. Aspirin's antithrombotic and anti-inflammatory properties may help prevent thrombus extension, recurrent embolization, and re-occlusions, contributing to reduced END incidence [37]. While HT is generally associated with worsened clinical outcomes in IS patients, our study found that although antiplatelet use increased the risk of HT, this was confined to asymptomatic cases and did not translate into worse outcomes. This aligns with other studies suggesting that pre-stroke antiplatelet use does not adversely affect overall prognosis despite increased HT risk [38]. Interestingly, even though the reduction in initial stroke severity with antiplatelet use was significant only in AT stroke, improved functional outcomes at three months were observed across all stroke subtypes.

This suggests that factors beyond initial stroke severity, such as reduced platelet activation and lower END incidence, may contribute to better long-term outcomes [39,40].

Limitations

This study has several limitations. Detailed information regarding the specific antiplatelet drugs used, their dosages, and the number of agents was not available.

Despite efforts to control for confounding factors using multivariable analyses, residual bias due to baseline characteristic imbalances may still exist. Additionally, we did not assess initial infarct size, which could have provided more insight into the relationship between antiplatelet use and stroke severity.

Conclusion

Pre-stroke antiplatelet therapy appears to reduce initial stroke severity in patients with AT stroke and is associated with decreased risk of END and improved functional outcomes at three months across all stroke subtypes. Although antiplatelet use increases the risk of asymptomatic HT, it does not adversely affect overall prognosis, suggesting a net clinical benefit in acute ischemic stroke management.

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